

Andrew Williamson Wolfson Fellow for 1968-9

Summary of field work in Iran August 1968 to May 1969

After preparatory work in Teheran I started field work in late September 1968 and worked until mid December on archaeological survey in inland Fars, Seistan and Kerman. From mid December until Mid February I was at Siraf. From mid February until the end of April I surveyed along the coast of the Persian Gulf and in the Kur river river basin. During May I worked in Shiraz and Teheran on the pottery from my survey.

a) Prehistoric sites.

Pottery was collected from prehistoric sites visited in the course of my survey. The material from the Inland sites was handed over to Mr. W. Sumner who is studying the prehistoric pottery of Fars. Of particular interest are five sites near the coast of the Persian Gulf with pottery corresponding to Yahya VI of a middle to late third millenium date. Three of these, near Minab, on Hormuz island and near Bushehr seem to have been small port sites.

b) Islamic coastal sites.

Work on the coast proved the most fruitful part of my survey. A large number of extensive and interesting sites of early Islamic and preSafavid date were discovered and visited. The Minab area was remarkable for its profusion of extensive sites and included kiln mounds for mediaeval sgraffiatô wares. Further along the coast a number of early Islamic sites associated with oyster debris attested to mediaeval pearling operations. The great sites of Hormuz, old Hormuz, Kung and Qish were all visited. The size of the site on Qish island proved much larger than previously recorded and was of very great extent in the main Siraf occupation period.

Map to illustrate routes taken in survey 1968-9 and proposed routes for 1969-70 (dotted lines)

SCALE
1:3,500,000

c) Inland sites.

Sites were plentiful in most of Fars and especially in the Kur river basin. There was interesting evidence of mediaeval industrial activity in pottery, glass and iron manufacture. However, in Kerman, the qanat irrigated areas of Fars and in Seistan sites of mediaeval date were rare. However in Seistan and Kerman I was able to locate what I believe were the mediaeval capitals of these provinces.

1) Zaranj. To the East of Zabol on the ridge occupied by Bibi Dust and Burg i Afghan (Stein Innermost Asia II p. ⁹³⁶ ff) among the high late mounds which have exclusively taken up the attention of earlier scholars, low mounds of early mediaeval date stretch for almost six kilometres. The most common pottery was decorated with underglaze painting using an iron pigment in limp spirals reminiscent of Tang painted stoneware.

2) Sirjan. The site is some ten kilometres from the citadel formerly identified with old Sirjan. In the tenth century A.D. al Muqaddasi described the city as larger than Shiraz and mounding which today covers over three by two kilometres makes it the largest surviving early Islamic site in Iran. The surface pottery is of pre Seljuk date. The site is unique in its surface combination of the whole range of Siraf wares including the Far Eastern with a very wide variety of East and North Eastern Iranian wares including the 'Samanid' slip painted pottery. I hope in September 1969 to excavate three glazed pottery kilns of a very early date and also a stratigraphic sondage to establish the dating of those wares absent from Siraf by their stratigraphic association with pieces of known date from Siraf. If successful this would open up the whole of the East of the Iranian plateau in this period to a scientific excavated chronology

d) Islamic unglazed painted ware.

I have recovered large quantities of Islamic unglazed painted ware from sites all over Southern Iran in a wide variety of techniques and patterns. At the end of July I hope to produce for the editor of Iran a short article on this little known range of pottery.

e) Chinese pottery and porcelain.

I know of over 45 sites on all parts of the Iranian plateau which produce Chinese pottery, mostly celadons. However only three of these sites have pottery dating from before the introduction of Chekiang celadon in the late Sung period (Istakhr, Kerman, Sirjan.) On the coast Chinese ware is very common and I have collected over 7,000 sherds. Of the greatest importance are two sites with over 2,000 sherds of late Sung material but with no blue and white.

f) Islamic coarse pottery.

The distribution of unglazed pottery has proved just as interesting as that of the glazed wares and I am devoting time to its study.

g) Pottery Kilns.

The largest battery of pottery kilns I have discovered are the fifteen close together at Sirjan. Besides these I have located kilns producing mediaeval green glazed ware, moulded ware carved ware, and sgraffiato decorated ware.

h) Steatite.

I hope in collaboration with David Whitehouse to investigate the question of the source of this material.

I have from time to time deposited fuller accounts of the progress of my research with Mr. Stronach.

I hope that in the next year I shall be able to fill in the main gaps in my survey coverage and especially to extend my investigation of the coast.